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Salinity Gradients for Coastal Monitoring

2021

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PACIFIC NORTHWEST NATIONAL LABORATORY
operated by
BATTELLE
for the
UNITED STATES DEPARTMENT OF ENERGY
under Contract DE-AC05-76RL01830

Printed in the United States of America

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Prepared for
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Abstract

Coastal waters serve as the interface between the open oceans and the land; therefore, they encompass many unique habitats and serve important human needs. Unfortunately, coastal waters are also more susceptible to chemical, heat, and sedimental pollution. Coastal monitoring is an important process that helps provide information on the water quality, health, and overall state of their ecosystems. Coastal sensors commonly measure variables such as temperature, conductivity, pH, salinity, dissolved oxygen, fluorescence due to chlorophyll, turbidity, nitrates, and phosphate concentration. Wireless sensing networks are at the forefront of marine monitoring systems as they offer consistent and high-quality data and are much more cost effective than traditional models of monitoring. In a marine environment, a significant challenge to sensor reliability and longevity is biofouling. Biofouling is the process in which biological matter or living organisms accumulate on man-made surfaces where they are unwanted/prohibitive to the structures' function. Another important consideration when developing a coastal monitoring system is the type of platform or anchoring system it will need to remain secure. The most common methods for attachment include anchored buoys, moored locations, seabed, and on sea vessels. Powering underwater coastal monitoring systems can present issues as in many areas there is insufficient infrastructure to easily power these systems from shore. This means that systems have a powering system that allows them to be independent and reliable, such as solar power. This report analyzes the feasibility of salinity gradient energy which could potentially eliminate the issues associated with other forms of power generation. Data is presented to estimate the total required membrane surface area of a coastal monitoring unit to evaluate its potential feasibility in single and multi-sensor coastal monitoring systems.

Summary

The objective of this analysis was to evaluate the feasibility of using salinity gradient energy to power coastal water sensors. Coastal monitoring provides crucial information on the water quality, health, and overall state of the interconnected ecosystems which are particularly susceptible to pollution. Powering underwater coastal monitoring systems is challenging because there is often insufficient infrastructure to easily power these systems from shore. This means that coastal monitoring devices need a powering system that allows them to be independent and reliable. Salinity gradient energy is a promising technology that could be used to power coastal sensors without the drawbacks of existing types of power generation. This report provides technical specifications (power requirements, temperature, pressure, and temperature measurement range, accuracy, response time, etc.) for 7 types of coastal sensors including temperature, dissolved oxygen, nitrate, phosphate, pH, turbidity, and conductivity. Using an estimate of maximum net power generation of salinity gradient membranes to be 2.7 W/M^2 , the total required membrane surface area of a coastal monitoring unit was determined and used to evaluate its potential feasibility. Less than 3 square meters of total salinity gradient membrane would be feasible to implement in a coastal monitoring setting since membranes are stacked upon each other, maximizing surface area in a relatively small volume. The power requirements of single variable sensors range from 0.045 watts ($0.003\text{A} \cdot 15\text{V}$) to 7.5 watts ($0.625\text{A} \cdot 12\text{V}$), which would mean the total membrane surface area would need to be at least 2.78 m^2 in order to power the nitrate sensors with the greatest power requirements. An example multi-sensor system using a Seabird dissolved oxygen, conductivity, temperature, turbidity, nitrate, and phosphate sensor array requires a total wattage figure of 12.59 W would require a maximum of 4.66 m^2 of salinity gradient membrane. In conclusion, a salinity gradient unit would feasibly be able to meet the power requirements of even multi-sensor arrays with a reasonably sized power generation unit.

Acknowledgments

Funded through the Student Research Apprenticeship Program, US Department of Energy, Pacific Northwest National Lab, WA

Acronyms and Abbreviations

DO (Dissolved Oxygen)

FNU (Formazin Nephelometric Units)

PRO (Pressure Retarded Osmosis)

RED (Reverse Electrodialysis)

WSN (Wireless Sensing Network)

VDC (Voltage Direct Current)

UV (Ultraviolet)

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1.0_Introduction

1.1_Importance of Coastal Monitoring

Coastal waters serve as the interface between the open oceans and the land, a result of which is that they encompass many unique habitats and serve important human needs. Coastal waters are distinct from open ocean or freshwater bodies as they are the mixing ground of fresh water and salt water. This creates brackish water in many coastal areas which is naturally found nowhere else in the world. As a result, coastal areas are incredibly diverse, providing breeding habitats for up to 85% of U.S. migratory birds and other marine animals such as fish, sea turtles, and marine mammals (“Coastal Waters” US EPA O.R.D. 2017). Unfortunately, coastal waters are also more susceptible to chemical, heat, and sediment pollution because of their intersection with the land and sea. For that reason, coastal monitoring is an important process that helps provide information on the water quality, health, and overall state of these ecosystems. This information is primarily used to not only monitor the state of coastal environments but also to guide human action in response to both natural and anthropogenic events. Continuous monitoring via the use of small-scale, self-powered monitoring devices is the most effective and inexpensive way to observe coastal areas with minimal environmental impact.

1.2_Wireless Sensing Networks (WSN) for Coastal Monitoring

Wireless sensing networks are at the forefront of marine monitoring systems as they offer consistent and high-quality data and are much more cost-effective than traditional models of monitoring (Zeng et al. 2019). Other methods of water quality monitoring involve analyzing water samples in a lab, using expensive remote sensing technology, or monitoring indicator species within an ecosystem. Analyzing water samples requires personnel to physically obtain samples, making it an expensive and low sample rate process. Remote sensing technology, such as sonar, can only measure certain parameters of water quality and have large upfront costs. Monitoring of indicator species within an ecosystem is a highly imprecise method for determining water quality and involves direct human observation which makes it less reliable and more expensive. Wireless sensor networks are the best suited for coastal monitoring applications since they allow for high sampling rates, quality data, are low maintenance, and are cost-effective (Jiang et al. 2009).

Wireless sensing networks function off a number of levels, ranging anywhere from the bottom level of the physical monitoring units to the top level where data is actually displayed and analyzed. Data is initially produced when sensors measure parameters from their environment and convert that information into data of a usable form. From there the information is processed through an on-board data logging system and is transmitted wirelessly from the monitoring device (Xu et al. 2019). Figure 1 displays the components of a monitoring system and the flow of information within the device.

Figure 1. Remote monitoring system diagram. Displays transfer of energy and information between components. (Source: Xu, 2019; <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/19/7/1711#>)

1.3_Challenges of Sensing Networks in Marine Environments

1.3.1_Sensor Biofouling Problem and Prevention

Biofouling is the process in which biological matter or living organisms accumulate on man-made surfaces where they are unwanted/prohibitive to the structures' function. In the case of coastal sensing systems, biofouling is a significant issue as the function or accuracy of many sensors can be easily impaired by biological matter. Currently, there are a few strategies that are employed to mitigate biofouling which include the use of bio-deterrent materials, shutters, and bio-wipers. Bio-deterrent materials are a classification of substances that at a chemical level are resistant to biological compounds binding to them. Some examples of these deterring materials include sterling silver, 90/10 copper, and brass. These types of material can provide a basic layer of protection against biofouling, however mechanical solutions are often more effective. Shutters are mechanical devices that allow for sensitive components of sensors to be shut off from the outside environment entirely until they are needed to sample the water. Bio-wipers are another mechanical anti-fouling system that function by forcibly removing biological debris from sensors at regular intervals using a small wiping system. Shutter and bio-wiping systems are very effective in preventing biofouling, however, there are some drawbacks to their use. Shutters, like any mechanical device, can stop working and completely render a sensor useless until a technician can repair it. Bio-wipers need to be made from materials that will not scratch or damage the lens or operating surface of a sensing system. Additionally, all the anti-fouling strategies outlined

above must be implemented at the design stage of the sensor, meaning the selection of sensors is limited when working to mitigate biofouling. Figure 2 depicts a bio-wiper system designed for an optical dissolved oxygen sensor. The photo in Figure 3 is of a shutter system on a sensor array in the open position.

Figure 2. Example sensor bio-wiper device. (Source: <https://www.fondriest.com/zebra-tech-ponsel-digisens-dissolved-oxygen-sensor-hydro-wiper.html>)

Figure 3. Example shutter system on a sensor array. (Source: <https://www3.mbari.org/bog/Projects/MOOS/shutter/>)

1.3.2_Anchoring/Attachment

An important consideration when developing a coastal monitoring system is the type of platform or anchoring system it will need to remain secure. The most common attachment methods include anchored buoys, moored locations, seabed, and on sea vessels (Albaladejo et al. 2017). Each method has certain advantages and disadvantages however for coastal monitoring applications, anchored buoys and moored locations are the most advantageous. Anchored buoys work by having a buoy on the water surface with an anchor holding the buoy in place on the seabed. Sensors can easily be attached at any depth along the anchor line and data gathered transmitted from above the water onboard the buoy (Albaladejo et al. 2010). The biggest disadvantage of a

buoy system is that they create surface level obstructions, which in some circumstances can present issues for sea vessels. Figure 4 depicts the structure of an anchored buoy sensor system in several formats.

Moored attachments are an even simpler approach to securing monitoring devices since they do not require any extra equipment and does not create new sea surface obstructions. Most common attachment sites include pylons, docks, and other manmade structures. Limitations of this securing method are the limited number of pre-existing sites and decreased flexibility with location and depth.

Figure 4. Common configurations of buoys used in aerial communication wireless sensor networks. (Source: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3231109/>)

1.3.3_System Powering

Powering underwater coastal monitoring systems can present issues as in many areas there is insufficient infrastructure to easily power these systems from shore. This means that systems have a powering system which allows them to be independent and reliable. Current technologies, such as solar, are being utilized to power these types of monitoring system, however they have limitations which need to be addressed ("Water Quality Buoy Vertical Profiling System For Coastal Applications" ysi.com). Solar power can only be utilized when it is above water, meaning that systems are constrained to using a buoy anchoring system. Additionally, power is only available when there is sufficient sunlight, limiting solar powered systems to certain geographic locations with sufficient sunlight year-round. Figure 5 displays a solar powered coastal monitoring buoy. To eliminate these constraints, a power generation system which can work independently, consistently, and in any location is ideal for coastal monitoring applications. This report analyzes the feasibility of salinity gradient energy which could potentially eliminate the issues associated with other forms of power generation. It could allow for consistent and completely remote power generation for large networks of monitoring devices in any coastal locations. For more background information on salinity gradient energy refer to section 3.

Figure 5. Example of solar powered coastal monitoring system
(Source: <https://www.ysi.com/buoy-vertical-profiling-system>)

2.0_Oceanographic Sensors

2.1_General Types

Water quality is a term that is generally used to describe the overall health of a given area or body of water however, it is not a single parameter of water that can be easily measured. The quality of water is described by several chemical, physical, and biological characteristics that vary from both internal and external factors ("What is water quality?" NOAA). Monitoring systems designed to measure the quality of bodies of water have to use an array of sensors to get an accurate picture. The sensors used typically measure temperature, conductivity, pH, salinity, dissolved oxygen, fluorescence due to chlorophyll, turbidity, nitrates, and phosphate concentration("Detection and Monitoring of Marine Pollution Using Remote Sensing Technologies" intechopen.com; Albaladejo et al. 2010). There are countless other types of niche sensors used for specific applications, but these sensors can be applied to any marine or coastal environment. Sensor selection is dependent on the requirements of the user and the constraints of the environment (Albaladejo et al. 2017). Together, combinations of these sensors can be used to measure multiple parameters of the make-up of water that can then be interpreted as a general index of water quality.

2.2_Common Coastal Measurements

2.2.1_Temperature Sensing

Temperature sensors are commonly used in a wide variety of underwater monitoring applications as temperature data is highly versatile. There are several methods for measuring temperature, ranging from the use of a glass-mercury thermometer to electrical resistance-based temperature sensors. Thermistors, a resistor whose resistance is dependent on temperature, are regularly used in underwater temperature sensors as they can provide accurate, digital outputs over a wide range of temperatures. Thermistors read temperature by measuring how much their electrical resistance changes, this can then be interpreted as a temperature using experimental data gathered for each thermistor material type. Unlike other types of temperature sensors, the resistance and temperature of a thermistor do not form a linear relationship ("Thermistor Basics" teamwavelength.com). A typical thermistor resistance-temperature curve and thermistor are shown in Figures 6 and 7, respectively.

Temperature readings from coastal sensing units can be utilized to detect both long-term patterns as well as short-term changes. This means everything from small changes in overall surface sea temperature rising to heat pollution coming from upriver sources can be detected. These temperature changes are significant as they can affect the flora and fauna living in coastal ecosystems.

Figure 6. An example thermistor resistance-temperature curve.

(Source: <https://www.teamwavelength.com/thermistor-basics/#:~:text=A%20thermistor%20is%20a%20resistance,such%20as%20epoxy%20or%20glass>)

Figure 7. An example sensor thermistor. (Source:

<https://www.seeedstudio.com/blog/2020/10/27/thermistors-ntc-and-ptc-thermistors-explained>)

Table 1. Temperature Sensors

Parameter	Seabird (SBE 38)	Seabird 3F	Seametrics TempHion (pH/Temp/ORP)	Eureka Manta 2	Seametrics T1 (Temp/Pressure)
Link	https://www.seabird.com/sbe-38-digital-oceanographic-thermometer/product?id=60762467703	https://www.seabird.com/sbe-3f-3plus-3s-oceanographic-temperature-sensor/product-downloads?id=60762467708	https://www.seametrics.com/product/tempHion-phorp/	https://www.waterprobes.com/temperature-water-sondes	https://www.seametrics.com/product/t1/
Power Requirements	8 - 15 VDC at 15 mA average for RS-232 output	11-16 VDC, 25 mA	9 - 15 VDC		9 - 15 VDC, Reading: 3 mA, Sleep: 250 μ A
Weight	0.9 kg (2.0 lb) in air, 0.5 kg (1.1 lb) in water	0.6 kg (1.3 lb) in air, 0.3 kg (0.7 lb) in water (<i>Aluminum housing</i>); 0.9 kg (2.0 lb) in air, 0.6 kg (1.3 lb) in water (<i>Titanium housing</i>)	0.4 kg (0.8 lb)		0.4 kg (0.8 lb)
Temperature Range		-5 - 35 $^{\circ}$ C (23 - 95 $^{\circ}$ F)	0 - 55 $^{\circ}$ C (32 - 131 $^{\circ}$ F)	-5 - 50 $^{\circ}$ C (23 - 22 $^{\circ}$ F)	-5 - 70 $^{\circ}$ C (23 - 158 $^{\circ}$ F)
Pressure / Depth Range	<10,500 m (34,449 ft)	<6,800 m (22,310 ft) (<i>Aluminum housing</i>), <10,500 m (34,449 ft) (<i>Titanium housing</i>)	210 m (689 ft)		
Measurement Range	-5 - 35 $^{\circ}$ C	-5 - +35 $^{\circ}$ C	0 - 55 $^{\circ}$ C (32 -131 $^{\circ}$ F)		-5 $^{\circ}$ - 70 $^{\circ}$ C (23 - 158 $^{\circ}$ F)
Accuracy	\pm 0.001 $^{\circ}$ C	\pm 0.001 $^{\circ}$ C	\pm 0.2 $^{\circ}$ C	\pm 0.1 $^{\circ}$ C	\pm 0.2 $^{\circ}$ C
Output	Celsius, Fahrenheit, Kelvin	\pm 0.5 V square wave	Celsius, Fahrenheit, Kelvin	Celsius, Fahrenheit	
Response Time	500 msec	0.065 sec \pm 0.010 sec (1.0 m/s water velocity); 0.070 sec \pm 0.010 sec (0.5 m/s water velocity)			
Diameter	3.9 cm (1.5 in)	4.8 cm (1.7 in)	1.9 cm (0.8 in)		1.9 cm (0.8 in)
Height	25.7 cm (10.1 in)	27.0 cm (10.7 in)	45.6 cm (18.0 in)		17.4 cm (6.9 in)

2.2.2_Dissolved Oxygen (DO) Sensing

Dissolved oxygen (DO) is a vital water quality indicator of coastal ecosystems since DO levels determine which fish, mollusks, and other underwater organisms can survive (Florida). Dissolved oxygen is a measure of the amount of oxygen found in a given sample of water and it is typically measured in mg/L (“Indicators of Dissolved Oxygen” US EPA O.W. 2013b). Oxygen is primarily introduced into water when wind or naturally fast-moving water creates an aerating effect that allows oxygen from the atmosphere to dissolve into the water (“What is water quality?” NOAA). Insufficient DO within a given aquatic ecosystem can lead to widespread die-offs of aquatic life.

There are three types of sensors capable of measuring DO levels within the water: galvanic, polygraphic, and optical sensors. These sensors work in different ways; however, optical DO sensors are best suited for coastal monitoring as they are lower maintenance and have no minimum flow rate. Optical sensors function by utilizing a sensor cap filled with luminescent dye which glows red when exposed to blue light. Dissolved oxygen within the water interferes with the luminescence in an effect called “quenching” which reduces the light emitted. The magnitude of luminescence can then be measured by a photodiode and compared to a reference reading to produce an accurate reading of DO levels (Prajapati 2018). Figure 8 is a diagram of the components of an optical DO sensor.

Figure 8. Optical dissolved sensor components.
(Source: <https://www.hach.com/PowerLDO>)

Table 2. Dissolved Oxygen Sensors

Parameter	Campbell Scientific	Seabird SBE 43	Seametrics	Edaphic Scientific	Eureka Manta 2
Link	https://www.campbellsci.com/cs511-l	https://www.seabird.com/sbe-43-dissolved-oxygen-sensor/product-downloads?id=60762467728	https://www.seametrics.com/product/dosensor/?gclid=EAlaQobChMlopia1umc8glVpjytBh2sdQMN_EAMYAiAAEgJsU_D_BwE	https://edaphic.com.au/oxygen/dissolved-oxygen-deep-sea-sensor/	https://www.waterprobes.com/optical-do
Power requirements		6.5 - 24 VDC; 60 milliwatts	9 - 15 VDC External Power Pack Required	12 VDC; 55 ±10 mA	
Weight	0.8 kg (1.8 lb) including sensor and shipping kit	0.5 kg (1.1 lb) in air; 0.1 kg (0.2 lb) in water		0.26 kg (0.6 lb)	
Temperature Range	0 - 50 °C (32 - 122 °F)		0 - 55 °C (32 - 131 °F)		
Pressure / Depth Range	70.5 m (231 ft)	600 m (19,699 ft)	70.5 m (232 ft)	2,000 m (6,563 ft)	200 m (656 ft)
Measurement Range	0.5 - 50 ppm (for O ₂)	120% of surface saturation in all natural waters (fresh and salt)	0 - 25 ppm	0 - 150% saturation; 0 - 20 mg/L	0 - 200% saturation; 0 - 20 mg/L
Accuracy	± 2%	± 2%	± 1% or 0.02 ppm (whichever is greater)	± 2% saturation	± 2 mg/L; ± 2% saturation
Output	33 mV ± 9 mV (100% saturation); < 2 mV (0% saturation)	0-5 VDC (SBE 43), frequency (SBE 43F)		0 - 5 VDC	
Response Time	5 min from 0 - 100% oxygen	2 - 5 sec for 0.5-mm membrane; 8 - 20 sec for 1.0 mm membrane	Less than 60 sec for 95%	10 sec for 63%	
Minimum Water Velocity	5 cm s ⁻¹ (2 in s ⁻¹) across membrane				
Minimum Submersion Depth	6.35 cm (2.5 in)				
Diameter	5.72 cm (2.3 in)	6.99 cm (2.8 in)	4.22 cm (1.7 in)	2.5 cm (1.0 in)	
Height	17.78 cm (7.0 in)	29.9 cm (11.8 in)			

2.2.3_Nitrate Sensing

Nitrates are organic compounds primarily composed of the nitrogen found within the atmosphere. In nature, these nitrates can only be converted or “fixed” from atmospheric nitrogen by certain plants and bacteria within the soil. However, large-scale modern agriculture has led to the mass production of synthetic nitrates which are used in fertilizers and spread on crops. These nitrates are then carried by runoff into streams and rivers which eventually carry them into coastal aquatic ecosystems. Because of the use of nitrates in agriculture, their concentration in water fluctuates seasonally as fertilizer usage changes year-round (“Major issues and findings: Nutrients in surface water” USGS). The abundance of these nutrients within the water causes algal blooms which can quickly cover the surface of the water. Figure 9 displays the significantly disrupted appearance of surface water during an algal bloom. This in turn blocks the sunlight from reaching the water, killing aquatic plants and depleting the dissolved oxygen, creating what is known as a dead zone(August and Alum). Additionally, high nitrate concentrations can be toxic to warm-blooded animals such as humans (“5.7 Nitrates - Monitoring & Assessment” US EPA).

Figure 9. Surface water impacted by algal bloom.

(Source: <https://www.unep.org/news-and-stories/story/what-do-you-know-about-algal-blooms>)

Nitrate concentration can be measured in one of three ways: ion-selective electrodes, in-situ wet chemistry, or optical (UV) based sensors. Optical nitrate sensors are best suited to coastal monitoring applications as they require little maintenance and are least susceptible to biofouling. Optical sensors operate because nitrate ions absorb UV light, light at wavelengths under 220 nm. Photodiodes are then capable of measuring the magnitude of light and using experimental data produce nitrate concentration (“Nutrient Monitoring - Nitrate” nextsens.com 2018).

Table 3. Nitrate Sensors

Parameter	Seabird DEEP Suna	Seabird DEEP V2 Suna	EXO NitraLED	OTT ecoN	TriOS NICO UV
Link	https://www.seabird.com/nutrient-sensors/suna-ocean-nitrate-sensor/product?id=60762467724	https://www.seabird.com/nutrient-sensors/suna-v2-nitrate-sensor/family?productCategoryId=54627869922	https://www.ysi.com/nitraled?utm_source=NitraLED&utm_medium=web&utm_campaign=Wordstream&qclid=EA1aIQobChMI-sqF_dK28gIVLD2tBh0dzg4QEAAAYASAAEglmnfD_BwE	https://www.ott.com/products/water-quality-2/ott-econ-2439/	https://www.fondriest.com/trios-nico-uv-nitrate-sensor.htm
Power requirements	7.5 W (0.625 A at 12 V) nominal	8 - 18 VDC, 7.5 W (0.625 A at 12 V) nominal		12-24 VDC, ≤ 7 W	≤ 7 W
Weight	1.8 kg (4.0 lb)	3.9 kg (8.6 lb)	0.07 kg (0.15 lb)	3 kg (6.6 lb)	3 kg (6.6 lb) stainless steel; 2 kg (4.4 lb) titanium
Temperature Range	-2 - 35 °C (28.4 - 95 °F)	0 - 35 °C (32 - 95 °F)	5 - 35 °C (41 - 95 °F)	2 - 40 °C (36 - 104 °F)	2 - 40 °C (36 - 104 °F)
Pressure / Depth Range	<2000 m (6561.7 ft)	500 m (1640.4 ft)	250 m (820.2 ft)	30.67 m (100.6 ft)	306.7 m (1,006.4 ft)
Measurement Range			0 - 10 mg/L-N	0.05 - 200 mg/L	0.5-60 mg/L NO ₃ -N (1mm path); 0.05-6 mg/L NO ₃ -N (10mm path)
Accuracy	2 μM (±0.028 mg/l-N) or ± 10% of reading		± 0.4 mg/L-N or 5% of reading		± (5% + 0.1 mg/L NO ₃ -N) with 10 mm path; ± (5% + 1 mg/L NO ₃ -N) with 1 mm path
Output			NO ₃ -N (Nitrate-N) mg/L	NO ₃ -N (Nitrate-N) mg/L	mg/L NO ₃ -N
Response Time			T95 < 30 sec		20 sec
Diameter	5.7 cm (2.2 in)	6.3 cm (2.5 in)	1.5 cm (0.6 in)	4.8 cm (1.9 inch)	4.8 cm (1.9 in)
Height	55.5 cm (22.0 in)	55.1 cm (21.7 in)	21.3 cm (8.4 in)	47 cm (18.5 in)	47 cm (18.5 in)

2.2.4_Phosphate Sensing

Phosphates are another organic compound naturally found cycling within ecosystems across the globe. Phosphates are found within rocks and sediment which are subsequently eroded and carried into bodies of water ("The phosphorus cycle"). However, very much like nitrates, phosphates have been made artificially to help facilitate agriculture in the use of fertilizers ("Understanding phosphorus fertilizers" extension.umn). As a result, excess phosphates are carried into freshwater streams/rivers and eventually into the ocean where they can cause eutrophication and, in some cases, dangerous algal blooms ("Indicators: Conductivity" US EPA O.W. 2013c). Similar to nitrates, phosphate concentrations fluctuate seasonally due to their presence in fertilizers. High phosphate concentrations can be deadly to humans as they can lead to calcifications within the body and weakening of the bones ("Phosphorus and Your Diet" kidney.org 2016). Figure 10 depicts the cycling of phosphorus within nature.

Figure 10. Phosphorus cycling.

(Source: <https://socratic.org/questions/how-does-erosion-affect-the-phosphorus-cycle>)

There are currently three phosphate sensing technologies available: optical, electrochemical, and biological. Optical sensing functions similarly to other types of optical sensors where light is beamed into the sample water and the reflectance of the phosphate ions is measured by a photodiode, giving the concentration ("Extracting Raman spectra from highly fluorescent samples with Scissors" spectroscopyeurope.com; Mapare et al. 2017; "SSRS, Shifted-Subtracted Raman Spectroscopy" spectroscopyeurope.com). Electrochemical sensors utilize ion-selective electrodes to generate a current in response to phosphate ions which can then be interpreted as a concentration (Liu et al. 1989). Biological sensors use a phosphate sensitive layer of enzymes attached to an electrode to observe the reaction between phosphate ions and the enzymes in terms of oxygen reduction (Petrucci et al. 1996).

Table 4. Phosphate Sensors

Parameter	Seabird HydroCycle Phosphate	Dartmouth Ocean Technologies
Link	https://www.seabird.com/hydrocycle-po/product?id=54721314201	https://dartmouthocean.com/products/phosphate-sensor
Power Requirements	10.5 - 18.0 V, 115 mA avg, 3 A max	1 - 10 watts
Weight	7.6 kg (16.8 lb)	Air 5.0 kg (11.0 lb), Water 1.8 kg (4.0 lb)
Temperature Range	0 - 35 °C (32 - 95 °F)	
Pressure / Depth Range	200 m (656.2 ft)	200 m (656.2 ft)
Measurement Range	0 - 2.3 µg P/L	0.15 - 120 µM, 15 ppb - 12 ppm
Accuracy		
Output		
Response Time		
Diameter	18 cm (7.1 in)	8.9 cm (3.5 in)
Height	56 cm (22.1 in)	44.2 cm (17.4 in)

2.2.5_pH Sensing

pH, sometimes termed the “power of hydrogen”, is a logarithmic scale ranging from 0-14 which quantifies the concentration of hydrogen ions within a solution (“pH and Water”). pH is an important metric of water quality that has become of greater interest in the past few decades due to a trend of ocean acidification. Ocean acidification is the long-term process in which the overall pH of the ocean decreases due to the dissolving of atmospheric carbon dioxide into the water (“What causes ocean acidification?” Natural History Museum). Dissolved carbon dioxide subsequently reacts with H₂O molecules to form carbonic acid which releases hydrogen ions into the water, therefore lowering the pH. However, the bigger issue for marine life is the corresponding consumption of carbonate molecules when pH is lowered, as carbonate is utilized by many aquatic organisms to build shells (“Ocean acidification” NOAA).

Figure 11. Bleached coral bed due to ocean pH alterations.

(Source: <https://www.nbcnews.com/science/environment/great-barrier-reef-hit-third-major-bleaching-event-five-years-n1166676>)

Ocean acidification has directly led to the bleaching a destruction of many coastal coral reef ecosystems (van Hooidonk et al. 2014). Figure 11 depicts a bleached coral reef ecosystem resulting from altered ocean pH.

The most used pH sensor is called a combination pH sensor, and it utilizes two electrodes, a reference and a measuring electrode ("Types of pH Sensors: What You Need to Know" sensorex.com 2019). The main component is the measuring electrode which is a silver-based wire contained in a glass bulb filled with a neutral solution of potassium chloride. This measuring electrode can measure pH by using the differing hydrogen ion concentrations inside and outside of the glass to create a small electrical voltage. This voltage can then be measured by the device and using experimental data converted into a pH value ("How do pH meters work? | Measuring acidity" explainthatstuff.com 2009). Figure 12 is a diagram of a pH measuring electrode.

Figure 12. Components of a pH measuring electrode. (Source: <https://group.chem.iastate.edu/Holme/augmented-reality-in-educational-laboratories/ph-meter/>)

Table 5. pH Sensors

Parameter	Campbell Scientific	Seabird SeaFET V2	Seametrics TempHion	Eureka Manta 2
Link	https://www.campbellsci.com/csim11	https://www.seabird.com/seafet-v2-ocean-ph-sensor/product?id=54627921732	https://www.seametrics.com/product/temp-hion-phorp/	https://www.waterprobes.com/ph-water-monitoring
Power Requirements			12 VDC - Nominal, 9-15 VDC - range	
Weight	0.5 kg (1 lb)	5.4 kg (11.9 lb) (Air), 0.1 kg (0.22 lb) (Water)	0.4 kg (0.8 lb)	
Temperature Range	0 – 80 °C (32 - 176 °F)	0 - 50 °C (32 - 122 °F)	0 – 55 °C (32 - 131 °F)	
Pressure / Depth Range	21.2 m (69 ft)	50 m (164 ft)	210 m (689 ft)	
Measurement Range	0 - 14	6.5 - 9.0 pH	0 - 14 pH	0 - 14 pH
Accuracy	±0.1% (over full range)	± 0.05 pH	± 0.2 pH units, 0.1% mV value	± 0.2 pH
Output	± 59 mV/pH unit		pH, mV	pH, mV
Response Time	95% of reading (in 10 sec)			
Diameter	3.0 cm (1.2 in)	11.4 cm (5.48 in)	1.9 cm (0.75 in)	
Height	17.8 cm (7.0 in)	54.9 cm (21.63 in)	45.6 cm (17.96)	

2.2.6_Turbidity Sensing

Turbidity is the measure of the relative clarity of a liquid. In the case of water quality turbidity is an important metric as it can be used to gauge the relative concentration of particulates within water. In nature, the turbidity of water is most often impacted by erosion and runoff of sediment from precipitation surrounding coastlines or freshwater bodies ("Turbidity and Water" USGS). Increased turbidity within water negatively impacts the health of an aquatic ecosystem as high turbidity leads to decreased light filtration for aquatic plants, harms the gill filtration of many fish species, and alters the breeding patterns of aquatic animals (Peterson and Gunderson). Turbidity can also harm human uses in coastal areas as cloudy water decreases the aesthetic quality of water and makes food and water processing more difficult. The most effective means for reducing turbidity is erosion control on land, this can be done through several methods including reforestation, construction of terraces, and storm drainage systems. Figure 13 represents the visual effect of turbidity on water quality.

Figure 13. Different levels of water turbidity in Formazin Nephelometric Units.
(Source: <https://www.usgs.gov/media/images/visualization-turbidity>)

The most basic form of turbidity measurements is done with a Secchi disk, a simple disk of alternating white and black coloration. The disk is lowered into the water until it is no longer visible, and the depth of the disk is recorded ("Measuring Lake Turbidity Using a Secchi Disk" Environmental Sampling). This simple testing can suffice for general observations of relative turbidity; however, a digital sensor can provide more specific and accurate data. Digital turbidity sensors function by sending a beam of light into the water which is then scattered by any suspended particles within the water. The photodiode then measures the intensity of light reflecting which correlates with the concentration of particles within the water ("Water Turbidity" aquaread.com).

Table 6. Turbidity Sensors

Parameter	Campbell Sci OBS501	Seabird ECO NTU	Eureka Manta 2	Seapoint Sensors
Link	https://www.campbellsci.com/obs501	https://www.seabird.com/eco-scattering-sensor/product?id=60762467719	https://www.waterprobes.com/turbidity	http://www.seapoint.com/stm.htm
Power Requirements	9.6 - 18 VDC, < 40 mA	7 - 15 VDC, 50 mA		7 - 20 VDC, 3 mA average, 5 mA peak
Weight	0.59 kg (1.3 lb)	1.3 kg (2.9 lb) (Air), 0.75 kg (1.7 lb) (Water)		0.08 kg (0.18 lb)
Temperature Range	0 - 40 °C (32 - 104 °F)	0 - 30 °C (32 - 86 °F)		0 - 65 °C (32 - 149 °F)
Pressure / Depth Range	100 m (330 ft)	6,000 m (19,685 ft)		6,000 m (19,685 ft)
Measurement Range	0 - 4,000 NTU	0 - 1,000 NTU	0 - 3,000 NTU	0 - 4,000 FTU
Accuracy	± 2% of reading or 0.5 NTU		± 2%	± 2% 0 - 1250 FTU; ± 5% 0 - 1600 FTU
Output	0 - 5 VDC	0 - 5 v	NTU	0 - 5.0 VDC, FTU
Response Time				
Diameter	4.8 cm (1.9 in)	6.3 cm (2.5 in)		2.5 cm (1.0 in)
Height	27 cm (10.6 in)	17.68 cm (7.0 in)		5.6 cm (2.2 in)

2.2.7_Conductivity Sensing

Conductivity is the measure of the ability of a given sample of water to pass an electrical current. The conductivity of a solution is directly proportional to the concentration of dissolved salts and other inorganic particles within the water. Since conductivity is related to the concentration of salt within the water, seawater is significantly more conductive than bodies of freshwater. Conductivity is an important metric of water quality as it can be a general indicator of inorganic pollution within an ecosystem ("Indicators: Conductivity" US EPA O.W. 2013a). Disturbances upriver from a coastal ecosystem can alter the short-term conductivity of the water if salts or other sediments enter the water. Salinity is important to aquatic life as aquatic flora and fauna are only capable of living within certain ranges of salinity for extended periods and fluctuations in salt concentration can negatively impact the ecosystem. An important consideration when measuring conductivity is that temperature differences can affect the conductivity of water, with higher temperatures leading to higher conductivity. Figure 14 illustrates the process in which salts dissolved in water correlate to conductivity.

Figure 14. Relationship between conductivity and salt concentration.
 (Source: <https://www.qmul.ac.uk/chesswatch/water-quality-sensors/electrical-conductivity/>)

Conductivity sensors work by using the principle of higher salt concentration within water correlating with higher conductivity of electricity. The sensor applies an alternating current to an electrode immersed within the water. This current is then carried by the water and into a second receiving electrode that measures the current. Higher salinity water corresponds to less resistance within the system and a greater returning current in the receiving electrode ("Conductivity Sensors" Yokogawa.com). Conductivity sensing is a simple yet highly effective method of measuring salinity within water.

Table 7. Conductivity Sensor

Parameter	SBE 4	Seametrics	Instrumart Analytical	Campbell Scientific
Link	https://www.seabird.com/sbe-4-conductivity-sensor/product?id=60762467707	https://www.seametrics.com/product/ct2x/	https://www.instrumart.com/products/36300/rosemount-analytical-model-228-conductivity-sensor	https://www.campbellsci.com/cs547a-l
Power Requirements	6 - 24 VDC; 18 mA at 6V, 12 mA at 10 - 24 V	12 VDC - Nominal, 9-15 VDC - range		
Weight	1.1 kg in air, 0.7 kg in water	0.5 kg (1.0 lb)	1.0 kg (2 lb)	0.08 kg (2.8 oz)
Temperature Range			120 °C (248 °F)	0 – 50 °C
Pressure / Depth Range	10,500 m	600 m	203 m (665 ft)	305 m (1,000 ft)
Measurement Range	0.0 - 7.0 S/m			0.005 - 7 mS/cm
Accuracy	± 0.0003 S/m	±0.5% of measured value (0 - 100,000 µS/cm)		±5%
Output	V square wave capacitively coupled			
Response Time	0.06 sec			
Diameter	7.7 cm (3.0 in)	1.9 cm (0.8 in)	3.76 cm (1.5 in)	2.54 cm (1.0 in)
Height	25 cm (9.9 in)	28.2 cm (11.0 in)	19.9 cm (7.8 in)	8.9 cm (3.5 in)

3.0_Salinity Energy Gradient

3.1_Overview

Salinity gradient is a term used to denote a difference in potential energy between water of different salt concentrations ("Salinity Gradient Energy Technology Brief" International Renewable Energy Agency irena.org). In nature, salinity gradients occur in locations where freshwater meets high-saline ocean water on the coast. The mixing of freshwater and saltwater releases energy, which in nature is typically lost as heat into the environment. However, salinity gradient energy is an emerging field of renewable energy that seeks to capture the energy of mixing freshwater and seawater to produce clean energy ("Osmotic Power" Wikipedia 2021). Salinity gradient energy is a very promising form of renewable energy because of the worldwide potential for power generation it poses, estimates placing it around $16.2\text{--}20.1 \times 10^3$ TWh/y (Yip et al. 2016). Despite these estimates likely being exaggerated, salinity gradient energy is still an incredibly promising prospect for future power generation. Currently, there are two primary viable technologies for capturing salinity gradient energy which include pressure retarded osmosis (PRO) and reverse electro dialysis (RED) (Yip et al. 2016).

3.2_Pressure Retarded Osmosis (PRO)

Pressure retarded osmosis functions based off the principle that low saline solutions will naturally move towards high saline solutions. By using this, a pressure retarded osmosis device using a semi-permeable membrane can create an area of high water pressure. Figure 15 demonstrates how a body of low saline water will move through a membrane into the high saline water, therefore creating greater water pressure on one side. This high water pressure can be released through a turbine which transfers the mechanical energy of the water into usable electrical energy.

Figure 15. Movement of water across a membrane with a salinity gradient.
(Source: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pressure-retarded_osmosis)

The process of pressure retarded osmosis is in many ways the opposite process to reverse osmosis, in which low saline water is produced via creating pressure on the high saline side and producing low saline solution (Pressure Retarded Osmosis - an overview, ScienceDirect Topics) ("What is Reverse Osmosis?" puretecwater.com). Currently, the main limiting factor to the

widespread use of pressure retarded osmosis in power generation is the large capital costs of the semipermeable membranes (Salinity Gradient Energy).

3.3_Reverse Electrodialysis (RED)

Reverse electrodialysis is another technology under development that uses entirely different mechanics to produce electricity from salinity gradients. RED technologies utilize stacks of alternating semi-permeable cathode and anode membranes, low saline and high saline solutions flow between these membranes alternately (Salinity Gradient Energy). The salinity gradient difference is then the driving force that causes the transport of positively and negatively charged ions across their respective membranes, therefore creating an electrical current that can be captured. The total electrical output of the system is determined by the sum of the potential difference over the entire stack of membranes (Salinity Gradient Energy). Figure 16 illustrates the structure of a reverse electrodialysis device, with alternating anode/cathode membranes and high/low concentration solutions flowing alternately through the membranes.

Figure 16. Diagram of Reverse Electro Dialysis Device

(Source: https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Schematic-illustration-of-reverse-electrodialysis-RED-for-salinity-gradient-power_fig1_338254548)

The current limitations of RED technologies are the large upfront costs of the membranes and the overall lifetime/function of the membranes in harsh conditions (“Salinity Gradient Energy” International Renewable Energy Agency). Biofouling, a phenomenon discussed in section 1.3, is especially an issue with RED because of the large surface area of membranes needed to facilitate ion diffusion. The buildup of organic and nonorganic material on the membranes leads directly to lower overall power output and potentially can break the system entirely.

3.4_Capacitive Mixing

Capacitive mixing is the least developed salinity gradient technology currently on the market; however, it does have certain advantages over the other technologies listed above. Capacitive mixing works in a completely different manner than RED or PRO technologies because it does

not use selective membranes, but rather a system of “charging” and “discharging” electrodes within solutions of different salinities (“Energy from Water” psu.edu/energyfromwater). The capacitive mixing process begins when an anode and cathode are immersed in a high salinity solution, mostly likely sea water (Hatzell et al. 2014). The capacitive electrodes are then “charged” with negatively and positively charged particles. Then the electrodes are moved to a low salinity solution, most likely fresh water, where the negatively and positively charged particles are “discharged” and create an electrical current that can be captured as usable power.

The biggest downside of capacitive mixing technologies is that they have only been tested at a lab-scale level, unlike RED or PRO which have both been tested at an industrial scale. This means there is much less available information on the power densities of such systems and or potential issues that arise when scaling up to generate more power (“Osmotic Power” Wikipedia, 2021). The advantage of capacitive mixing over other technologies is the removal of membranes from the system, therefore helping to reduce running costs and potential issues involving biofouling.

Figure 17. Steps of Capacitive Mixing power generation
 (Source: <https://sites.psu.edu/energyfromwater/technologies/capmix/>)

4.0_Coastal Sensor Technical Specifications

There are a number of essential ocean variables identified by the Global Observing System Expert Panels including oxygen, nutrients, inorganic carbon, transient tracers (marine animal abundance and distribution), particulate matter, nitrous oxide, dissolved organic carbon, and ocean color (Wang et al. 2019). Common sensors used in marine environments and their units of measurement are outlined in Table 8. Many of these variables can be measured with commercially available sensors. This paper presents details on 12 parameters for 7 commonly used types of sensors used in coastal monitoring. Table 1 includes information on 5 temperature sensors – Seabird SBE 38, Seabird 3F, Seametrics TempHion (pH / Temp / ORP multi-sensor), Eureka Manta 2, and Seametrics T1, (Temp / Pressure multi-sensor). Table 2 outlines information on 5 dissolved oxygen sensors – Campbell Scientific Seabird SBE 43, Seametrics, Edaphic Scientific, and Eureka Manta 2. Table 4 provides information on 5 phosphate sensors – Seabird DEEP Suna, Seabird DEEP V2 Suna, EXO NitraLED, OTT ecoN, and TriOS NICO UV. Table 5 includes information on 2 pH sensors - Seabird HydroCycle Phosphate and Dartmouth Ocean Technologies. Table 6 Outlines information on turbidity sensors - Campbell Scientific, Seabird SeaFET V2, Seametrics TempHion (pH / Temp / ORP multi-sensor), and Eureka Manta 2. Table 7 provides information on 4 conductivity sensors - Campbell Sci OBS501, Seabird ECO NTU, Eureka Manta 2, and Seapoint Sensor. Table 7 includes information on 4 conductivity sensors – SBE, 4 Seametrics, Instrument Analytical, Campbell Scientific.

Table 8. Common Marine Sensors and Units.(Albaladejo et al. 2010)ⁱ
<https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/12/7/9613>

Measurement Parameter	Measurement Unit(s)
Temperature	°C, °F
Pressure	mmHg
Salinity (Conductivity)	g/L
Water Speed	m/s
Turbidity	FTU (Formazin Turbidity Unit) NTU (Nephelometric Turbidity Unit) JTU (Jackson Turbidity Unit) mg/L SiO ₂
Chlorophyll	µg/L
Dissolved Oxygen	mg/L
Nitrate	mg/L
pH	pKa
Swell	Height (m); Direction (degrees)
Blue-Green Algae Phycocyanin	Relative Fluorescence Units
Ammonium / ammonia	Mg/l-N
Rhodamine	µg/L
Hydrocarbons	ppm

5.0 Feasibility Data Analysis

5.1_Feasibility Overview

Among the variety of sensors outlined in the tables above, there is significant variation in the power requirements of sensors within their respective categories and between categories. To calculate the energy being drawn by a sensor, its specified amperage and voltage must be used to calculate its wattage (“How is Wattage Calculated?” sciencing.com). Amperage and voltage are multiplied together to give a wattage value which can then be compared to the power output of salinity gradient energy systems. Currently, there is very little information surrounding the power densities of many salinity gradient technologies, however, some estimates place the current maximum net power generation of salinity gradient membranes to be 2.7 W/M². Using this estimate, the total required membrane surface area of a coastal monitoring unit can be determined and used to evaluate its potential feasibility.

5.2_Single Sensor Systems

Single sensor coastal monitoring solutions are not ideal for comprehensive water quality measurement; however, they are the most feasible and low power systems. Tables 2-7, found within section 4, give specifications of commercially available oceanographic sensors. The power requirements of the given sensors range from 0.045 watts (0.003A*15V) with the Seametrics T1 temperature sensor (Table 1), to 7.5 watts (0.625A*12V) with the Seabird DEEP Suna nitrate sensor models (Table 3). Given the current maximum net power density of salinity gradient energy systems being 2.7 W/m², this would mean the total membrane surface area would need to be greater than or equal to 2.78 m² to power the nitrate sensors with the greatest power requirements. Less than 3 square meters of total salinity gradient membrane would be feasible to implement in a coastal monitoring setting since membranes are stacked upon each other, maximizing surface area in a relatively small volume.

5.3_Multi-Sensor Systems

Utilization of multiple sensors within a single coastal monitoring system requires more power and usually takes up a larger physical space but gives a far more comprehensive measure of water quality. Using specifications from Tables 2-8 the maximum power requirements of a system utilizing all of the sensor types above can be calculated. Table 9 shows the power requirements of the sensor in each category with the greatest power demands.

Using the total wattage of 12.59 W from Table 9 and the power density of 2.7 W/m² for salinity gradient energy systems, an estimated maximum of 4.66 m² of salinity gradient membrane would be needed to power a fully equipped coastal monitoring unit. A salinity gradient unit could be able to meet these power requirements with a reasonably sized power generation unit. PCCELL is one of the few companies with commercially available reverse electrodialysis units, with their largest unit having 4 m² of membrane area, and nearly enough membrane area to power the ED 4000: Industrial Scale Electrodialyzer (“PCCELL ED 4000” ppcell.de). Small modifications to the monitoring device could reduce its power requirements enough that it would

function with a single system such as the ED 4000 produced by PCCELL. This could be accomplished by withholding the nitrate sensor from the coastal monitoring system, which accounts for around 60% of the overall power demands of the system and therefore the required generation from the salinity gradient power generation system.

Table 9. Highest Power Requirements of Sensors in Each Category

Sensor	Wattage (W)
Seabird SBE 43 (Dissolved Oxygen)	1.44 W
Seabird SBE 4 (Conductivity)	0.43 W
Seabird 3F (Temperature)	0.4 W
Seabird DEEP Suna V2	7.5 W
Seabird ECO NTU	0.75 W
Seabird Hydrocycle PO4	2.07 W
Total:	12.59 W

*All pH sensors run on internal batteries and do not list power requirements, therefore are not included within this table

Using a total wattage of 12.59 W from Table 9 and the power density of 2.7 W/m² for salinity gradient energy systems, it can be estimated a maximum of 4.66 m² of salinity gradient membrane would be needed to power a fully equipped coastal monitoring unit. A salinity gradient unit could possibly be able to meet these power requirements with a reasonably sized power generation unit. PCCELL is one of the few companies with commercially available reverse electrodialysis units, with their largest unit having 4 m² of membrane area, nearly enough membrane area to power the ED 4000: Industrial Scale Electrodialyzer (“PCCELL ED 4000” ppcell.de). Small modifications to the monitoring device could reduce its power requirements enough that it would function with a single system such as the ED 4000 produced by PCCELL. This could be accomplished by withholding the nitrate sensor from the coastal monitoring system, which accounts for around 60% of the overall power demands of the system and therefore the required generation from the salinity gradient power generation system.

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